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PEEK-Based Polymer Electrolyte with Tailored Morphology for Structural Battery Composites

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Introduction to Structural Battery Composites

Introduction to Structural Battery Composites

Materials used in 787 body

- Fiberglass
- Aluminum
- Carbon laminate composite
- Carbon sandwich composite
- Aluminum/steel/titanium

Total materials used
By weight

By comparison, the 777 uses 12 percent composites and 50 percent aluminum.

How can we enable the future of composites?

Introduction to Structural Battery Composites

- Carbon Fiber:
 - Stiffness and Strength
 - Electrode
 - Current Collector
- Polymer Matrix:
 - Binder and Load Transfer
 - Solid Electrolyte

Current State of Electrolytes

Liquid Electrolyte:

- Ionic Conductivity: 10^{-2} S/cm
- Lithium salt solubility
- Ideal wettability & viscosity
- Wide electrochemical stability window

Current State of Electrolytes

Solid Polymer Electrolyte (SPE):

- Ionic Conductivity: 10^{-6} S/cm
- No leakage
- Superior thermal stability
- Preventative for lithium dendrite growth

Solid Polymer Electrolyte Morphology Dependence

- Structure-Properties relationship
- Crystallites act as a barrier for lithium-ion transport
 - Inverse relationship with ionic conductivity

Functionalization of PEEK

- Sulfonic acid groups on the PEEK backbone enables morphological changes
 - Can be further functionalized with lithiation treatment

Thermal Stability of Functionalized PEEK

Morphology of Functionalized PEEK

- Lithiated PEEK displays ionomer peak, suggesting ionic conductivity
 - Sulfonated PEEK shows similar behavior

Thermomechanical Properties

- Sulfonated PEEK has highest storage modulus at ambient temperatures
- Lithiated PEEK has lowest storage modulus
 - Consistent at elevated temperatures

Thermomechanical Properties

How can we optimize the mechanical properties at temperature without compromising ionic conductivity?

Tailoring Morphological Properties

- Instead of fully functionalizing PEEK, selectively sulfonating the surfaces can allow for amorphous exterior and semi-crystalline interior
 - Balances the mechanical properties and ionic conductivity

Evaluating Dual Phase Functionalized Structure

- Surface sulfonation provides both amorphous and semi-crystalline structure simultaneously
- Confirms the balancing of properties of ionic conductivity and structure

Mapping PEEK Morphology

Crystallinity Behavior of Printed PEEK

- Highest crystallinity is found closest to the print bed
- Crystallinity decreases with increased thermal gradient from supercooling
- No sulfur present in the material

Mapping PEEK Morphology

Enabling Additive Manufacturing

- Printed PEEK mesh to maintain mechanical properties
- Functionalized PEEK infill to provide ionic conductivity

Grid

Triangle

Honeycomb

3D Honeycomb

 Printed Neat PEEK

Conclusions & Future Work

- Functionalization of PEEK can provide ionic conductivity to enable its use as a solid polymer electrolyte
- Additive manufacturing allows for selective enabling of crystalline and amorphous morphologies for optimized solid polymer electrolyte

Center for Science of Heterogeneous Additive Printing of 3D Materials

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80+ Faculty Involved

54+ Students have participated in and supported Center Projects

Cumulative Center Investment: \$5,580,113 (Phase I (5 years) - NSF, Members and Universities)

Current Full Member Leveraging: 28:1

Fused Deposition Manufacturing of Multiple Materials

Industry Membership

“SHAP3D brings together the best brains in the universities and industries to **develop technologies and convert** them into product developments for the benefits of society.” – *Greene Tweed*

“SHAP3D has active and engaged industrial members and **provides interaction** with multiple companies in the AM supply chain.” – *Integrity Integration*

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Mesoarchitectures in Topology Optimization

Thermoset Elastomer Printing using ARME Ram Printer Head

SHAP3DLP Printer

Graded Foams